

A Study on Perception of Farmers towards Agricultural Regulated Markets in Select Districts of Tamilnadu

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Abstract

Agriculture is the predominant occupation of more than one third of the population in India. They are engaged directly or indirectly in the agricultural activities. Indian economy is well supported by the development of agricultural sector. The contribution of Indian agricultural sector to the Gross Domestic Product of the country is highly significant. The agricultural products are much commercialized as the demand of these products has been constantly increasing with the growth of the population. Owing to the gap between demand and supply, the marketing of agricultural products needs to be regulated. The regulation of agricultural marketing has been focused by every country. It is mainly due to the control of the practices of middlemen. They make themselves a part of the agricultural products supply chain and cause the hike in the price of products. The farmers do not get fair prices for their products while the consumers have to pay higher prices for agricultural products. The difference between cost and price seems to be even greater than the cost. In the past, the farmers have sold their products to the consumers directly. Therefore, the farmers were able to get reasonable prices and the consumers were also benefited with lesser amount payable for these products.

Introduction

There have been number of transactions or operations for exchanging agricultural goods from the manufacturer to the consumer. The vital marketing functions involved are: buying, assembling, preparation for consumption and distribution. The demand for the product at the time of sale and the availability of storage determine the sale of agricultural products. The farmers sell the products either directly in the market or they keep the products in storage till the demand arises. Certain products are sold as it is gathered from the field or it may be cleaned, graded and processed by the farmer or the merchant of the village. Sometimes processing is done because consumers want it, or sometimes to conserve the quality of that product. The task of distribution system is to match the supply with the existing demand by whole selling and retailing in various points of different markets like primary, secondary or terminal markets.

In many cases, the farmers have to sell the products to the moneylenders from whom they have borrowed the loans. Local village traders also buy the products directly from the farmers. Apart from these modes of sale, the products are also sold in others ways. Weekly village market in and around the village of the farmers has been the major place of sale for the agricultural products of the farmers. If these outlets are not available, then produce might be sold at irregularly held markets in a nearby village or town, or in the mandi. In India, there are several Central Government Organizations, which are involved in agricultural marketing like, Commission of Agricultural Costs and Prices, Food Corporation of India, Cotton Corporation of India, Jute Corporation of India, etc. The specialized marketing bodies are available for rubber, tea, coffee, tobacco, spices and vegetables.

It is to be noted that around 70 per cent of the people are dependent on agriculture for their basic income. Earlier the farmers were concerned about the sale of their produce due to low quality. The Royal Commission on Agriculture found that there weren't enough marketing activities carried on by the farmers and suggested the formation of regulated markets and accordingly various market committees were incorporated. Regulated markets aim at the development of the marketing structure to ensure remunerative price to the farmers; reduce non-functional margins of the traders and commission agents; and narrow down the price spread between the producer and the consumer. To achieve these objectives, the government has made comprehensive and rapid expansion of regulated marketing systems. Besides, the regulated marketing system has proved as a good source of generating income for the marketing boards and for use in rural infrastructure. The first attempt for the regulation of markets in India dates back to 1897, when the Berar Cotton and Grain Markets Law was passed to purge marketing of many of its abuses. Since then various acts, rules and laws have been passed, and many committees and commissions have been appointed for facilitating and promoting the growth of regulated markets all over the country.

Regulated market is a wholesale market where buying and selling is regulated and controlled by the State Government through the market committee. It aims at the elimination of unhealthy and unscrupulous practices reducing marketing charges and providing facilities to producers and sellers in the market. The prevalence of various malpractices such as short- weights, excessive market charges, unauthorized deduction, adulteration of produce and the absence of machinery to settle disputes between sellers and buyers were recognized as the main hindrances in agricultural marketing. These defects and malpractices can be recovered by the establishment of regulated marketing their country may be regulated either by local bodies or under state legislation was suggested first in 1928 by the Royal Commission on Agriculture. The movement of regulation of market gained momentum only after 1930. The Bombay Agricultural Produce Market Act of 1939 was passed in respect of all agriculture produces viz., cereals, fibres, fruits, etc. Regulated markets are established under the provisions of the Agricultural Produce Marketing Committee Act of state governments.

Market Committee

Market committee is constituted in regulated markets with representatives from different sectors of society. The members of the market committee include farmers, traders, government local bodies and co-operatives. A market committee is generally constituted by 15 members viz., 10 from farmers, 3 from traders and 1 representative each from the government and local bodies.

Area of Operation of Regulated Market

The area of operation of regulated market is determined by the State Government in its notification in the official gazette. The area of operation denotes the boundaries or jurisdiction where the

concerned regulated market can extend its operations. The size of area of operations would vary from one regulated market to another depending upon the cultivation area, crops planted, number of farmers, merchants, etc. The area of operation may be confined within a municipal limit or district or a region.

Methods of Sales

The main purpose of regulated markets is to support the farmers in marketing their goods for reasonable prices. The agricultural products are sold in the regulated markets either by open auction or by close tender method. Under these methods of sales, a fair and competitive price for the produce is ensured and the cheating of farmers by market functionaries is prevented. The sale of agriculture produce in regulated markets is carried out under the supervision of an official of the market committee.

Licensing of Market Functionaries

It is mandatory that the market functionaries of the regulated market should obtain license from the market committee to carry on their business. The bylaw of the market committee provides for the procedure of maintaining the records and accounts by the licensed traders.

Market Levies or Fees

The market committee levies certain charges or fees for the farmers for trading in the regulated markets. These levies are calculated on the basis of value or volume of a commodity bought and sold in the markets. Cartload or truckload levy is also made on certain commodities.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of state regulation of agricultural markets was to protect farmers from the exploitation of intermediaries and traders and also to ensure better prices and timely payment for their produce. Over a period of time, these markets have, however, acquired the status of restrictive and monopolistic markets, providing no help in direct and free marketing, organized retailing and smooth raw material supplies to agro-industries. Exporters, processors and retail chain operators cannot procure directly from the farmers as the produce is required to be channelized through regulated markets and licensed traders. There is, in the process, an enormous increase in the cost of marketing and farmers end up getting a low price for their produce. Monopolistic practices and modalities of the state-controlled markets have prevented private investment in the sector. Post-harvest losses on fruits and vegetables increase due to varied reasons like lack of storage facilities, lack of adequate transport facilities and perishable nature of fruits and vegetables.

Farmers face so many difficulties while marketing their produce. The farm problem is usually associated with unstable and relatively low farm price and thereby low income. Agricultural output comes from many small units operated independently. The production to a great extent depends on monsoon condition. Today the lack of efficient modern regulated markets and the existing marketing problems faced by the farmers are the reason for the low market arrivals of agricultural produce in the regulated markets and low production of farm yields. The Madras Agricultural Produce Market Act had provided number of sections regarding the facilities and services in the regulated markets but in actual practices most of them are missing. Still some of the regulated markets are functioning well. Regulated markets are established with the prime objective of benefiting the farmers through better price and fair market practices deleting malpractices. Some of the farmers sell food products through regulated markets and rest of the products are sold to the village traders. Moreover as per regulations, brokers are not permitted in the regulated markets but still they act on behalf of the traders. The farmers also had a tough time because of

price fluctuations, poor storage, lack of information, unauthorized deductions, etc. Because of these numerous problems prevailing in the regulated markets the researcher made an attempt to study this topic. This study is undertaken in order to answer the following queries:

1. What could be the reason for the sale of products in the regulated markets?
2. What are the problems in storing the products in godowns?
3. To what extent the farmers are satisfied with the facilities / amenities provided by the regulated markets?
4. What are the problems encountered by the farmers in the regulated markets?

This study attempts to bring out the various aspects of the functioning and growth of regulated markets in the selected districts – Salem, Erode and Namakkal. It shows the evaluation of the performance of regulated markets and analysis of factors which determine the effective performance and inter-relationship among them.

Objectives of the Study

The present study aims at making an assessment on the working of the regulated markets in the selected districts. The following are the broad objectives of the study:

1. To know the functions of Regulated markets in India.
2. To examine the established marketing practices of the select regulated markets.
3. To assess the level of satisfaction of the farmers towards working of regulated markets in the select districts.
4. To identify the problems faced by the farmers in the regulated markets of the select districts.
5. To offer suitable recommendations for the efficient functioning of agricultural regulated markets in the select districts.

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses have been formulated for the present study:

1. The demographic variables have no significant influence on the sale of product after harvest – immediate sale and delayed sale.
2. The demographic variables do not significantly influence the way of transportation of products to the markets.
3. The relationship between demographic variables of the respondents and difficulties faced by the farmers in transporting the products is not significant.
4. There is no significant association between demographic variables and opinion on the overall performance of agricultural regulated markets.
5. The demographic variables do not have significant relationship with the problems in storing products in the godowns.
6. The level of satisfaction of farmers has not been significantly influenced by the demographic variables.

Scope of the Study

This study is undertaken to measure the performance of Agricultural Regulated Markets in select districts of Tamil Nadu. The study will provide the details regarding the sale of products in regulated markets, reason for immediate and delayed sale of agricultural products, problems in storing the products in godowns, satisfaction of farmers on facilities / amenities provided by regulated markets, satisfaction on overall performance of regulated markets and problems encountered by the farmers in marketing products in agricultural regulated markets. The scope of the study is confined to select districts – Salem, Erode and Namakkal.

Importance of the Study

The select districts – Salem, Erode and Namakkal are predominantly agricultural oriented districts. The agricultural produces of these districts are mainly sold through regulated markets. The Farmers of these districts are dependent on regulated markets for the sale of their produces. The working of regulated markets and the practices to be followed are the prime focus of the farmers. They expect that they could sell their produces for reasonable prices and with fair practices at the regulated markets. Their expectations and requirements could be fulfilled if the performance of regulated markets is good. Hence, this study has focused to examine the working of agricultural regulated markets in select districts and this study would provide necessary facts to the farmers and the performance of regulated markets could be improved in a better way.

Research Methodology

This study is systematically organized with scientific all analyze the data. Both descriptive and inferential analyses have been simultaneously employed to derive results with a view to fulfill the objectives of the study.

Pilot Study and Pre-Testing

The data required for analyzing the performance of agricultural regulated markets in select districts of Tamil Nadu has been collected by interview schedules. At the point of inception a pilot study was conducted and pre test was also conducted with a well defined interview schedule.

The main aim of the pilot study is to check the feasibility and reliability of the interview schedule which is used as a main tool of analysis. A tentatively well framed interview schedule was used to conduct interview with 60 respondents from three districts. The responses obtained were systematically transformed into the data base with suitable numerical coding. The Cronbache's Alpha method is applied on the primary responses and found that the reliability of more than 0.75 was observed. This shows the high reliability of the interview schedule circulated among the respondents. It is concluded that the interview schedule so framed is highly suitable in ascertaining the responses from the respondents.

Further, many a time it is not possible to examine every item in the population, and sometimes it is possible to obtain accurate results by studying only a part of total population. In such cases there is no utility of census survey. Under census method, each and every unit of the population or universe is studied. Census method will give more representatives, accurate and reliable results. Since it involves enormous amount of time and money, this method was not used in this research.

Pretesting is a method of checking that questions work as intended and are understood by those individuals who are likely to respond to them. However, detailed reports of appropriate methods to undertake pretesting are currently underrepresented within the literature. This documented approach to pretesting proved a vital stage in the scale development process, without which the item problems detected would have carried forward into the statistical analyses.

Sampling

Instead of obtaining information from each and every unit of the universe, only a small representative part is studied and the conclusions were drawn on that basis for the entire universe or whole population. Hence, in this research sampling method was used for collecting data. For this research Proportionate Stratified random sampling is used for collecting the data as the region wise population size exist.

The respondents from the 3 districts are the sampling units. Each District is treated as strata (Homogeneous sub groups or sub population). The sample size of the study is calculated with

the margin of error of 5 % and 95 % confidence level. The confidence level explains the extent of conformity of the results. It is expressed as a percentage and represents how often the true percentage of the population who would pick an answer lies within the confidence interval. The 95% confidence level means the results can be 95% certain. Here the researcher used 95% confidence level and the sample size is calculated as 410 for the population size of 2050. Further from each stratum the sub sample size is calculated proportionately.

Required Sample size for Group = SS

$$1 \frac{SS}{N}$$

N

$$Z^2 * p(1-p)$$

Where Sample size = C 2

Z = Standard normal value = 3.85 for 95 % confidence P = Percentage picking a choice normally 0.5, C = Level of significance = 5 % = 0.05

Therefore the minimum sample size = $3.85 * 0.5(1-0.5)/0.05 = 385$.

It is decided to take a sample of 20 per cent from each district of the population as detailed below:

Table 1.1 Sample Size

Districts	Market	Population	Sample
Salem	1	638	128
Erode	3	921	184
Namakkal	3	491	98
Total	7	2050	410

Instruments for Data Collection

One of the main research instruments for collecting primary data is interview schedule. Interview method helps in fulfilling several purposes, like measurement, descriptions and drawing inferences. The primary data is collected through the well framed interview schedule comprising optional type and Likert's five point scales.

Sources of Data

The primary data and the secondary data are the two types of data that are generally used in a research study. The Primary data refers to the first hand information collected by the investigator. Such data is original in character and is generated in a large number of surveys conducted, mostly by government and also by some individuals, institutions and research bodies. There are also several methods of collecting primary data like survey method, observation method to name a few. In this study, survey method is used to collect the primary data through a well designed interview schedule.

In this method, the researcher makes personal contacts with the informants either directly or indirectly and collects the required data. As the researcher is personally involved in collecting data, the information is more reliable and accurate.

Statistical Tools Used

The study results were analyzed by using various statistical tools. The data collected from the respondents were analyzed and presented in the form of tables. Charts have been used at various places as a statistical tool. The results are compared and analyzed by using descriptive analysis and

inferential analysis. Various statistical tools like non parametric freedman test, Garrett Ranking technique, chi-square test, average score analysis, independent sample t test, multiple regression analysis and structural model analysis were used appropriately.

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis, also termed as percentage analysis, was used for each question contained in the interview schedule mainly to ascertain the distribution of respondents under each category. Diagrams and charts are mainly used for clear understanding of the data collected in pictorial form. Pie-charts and bar charts were used for this purpose.

Limitations of the Study

1. Four hundred and ten respondents were interviewed to examine the performance of the regulated markets. In view of the time and money constraints it was not possible to contact more than selected number of respondents.
2. As the study is based on the primary data the accuracy depends on the corrections of the opinion given by the respondents.
3. The study reflects the performance of the selected regulated markets only. Hence, the results arrived at from the study may or may not be applicable to other districts.
4. As the farmers do not maintain detailed accounts of farm operations, the informations gathered from their memory only. Necessary errors verifications were made to reduce the biased information, wherever doubts arose.

Conclusion

The performance of agricultural markets in Salem, Erode and Namakkal Districts has been analyzed in this study. The reason for sale of goods in the regulated markets, problems faced by the farmers in marketing the products in regulated markets, level of satisfaction of farmers towards facilities / amenities provided by regulated markets and overall performance of regulated markets have been analyzed in this study. The results of the study reveals that farmers preferred to sell their products in the regulated markets for getting reasonable prices. In these regulated markets, the performance with reference to higher price has been found to be good. The problems faced by the farmers in storing and marketing the goods in regulated markets have been identified and it is understood that lack of adequate storage facilities and transportation facilities have been the most affecting problems of the farmers. It is strongly recommended that ensuring required storage facilities and transportation facilities would improve the performance of the regulated markets.

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